
Otherring Myself: Multiply Cultured, Differently Abled and Spiritually Hybrid

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Abstract: The author is convinced that other begins with one's own self. We are in fact not one monolithic self, but a multiplicity of even contradictory and ambiguous selves. At the postcolonial level, we can speak of the multiple discourses (conflicting and entangled narratives) governing us and so the othering of the other starts with the othering of my own self. For this we take two authors, Arundhati Roy and David Malouf, who will show the complex and nuanced identities of oneself. After realising this complex identities, we can try to enter into dialogue with the other, who is equally complex. This will help us to befriend the other.

Keywords: Arundhati Roy, David Malouf, Multiple Citizenships, Remembering Babylon, Multiple Identities.

Cite as: Pandikattu, Kuruvilla. (2021) Otherring Myself: Multiply Cultured, Differently Abled and Spiritually Hybrid (Version 1.0). Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies, July 2021(Vol 25/3), 25-39. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4459886>

Inspired by “*Intimate Enemy: Loss and Recovery of Self Under Colonialism*” (Nandy, 2015), I want to reflect on the fact that the other begins with my own self. We are in fact not one monolithic self, but a multiplicity of even contradictory and ambiguous selves. At the postcolonial level, we can speak of the multiple discourses (conflicting and entangled narratives) governing us and so the othering of the other starts with the othering of my own self. For this we take two authors, Arundhati Roy and David Malouf.

1. Multiple Citizenships and Commitments

Going beyond hybridity and identities, we study the committment to multiple citizenships drawing insights from Arundhati Roy and David Malouf. This section will enable us to appreciate the role played by the people who are marginalise and disprivileged in the post colonial discourses.

a. Arundhati Roy: Globalising Dissent

Arundhati Roy is one of the most familiar faces of India. Though her book *The God of Small Things* has made her famous, her later writings have made her controversial. “Contested and upheld, denounced and defended, global change wrought by the globalization of neoliberal economic doctrine has come to mean different things in different contexts—the promotion of world integration and opportunity for growth, as well as the reproduction of inequalities old and new” (Grewal, 2009: 143). The latter has provoked local–global activism from players with varying agendas, which in turn has enabled spirited debate in university classrooms and academic journals, international board rooms, and local communities, raising deep questions of human agency, social justice, and equity. We can situate Arundhati Roy’s work as part of the wider response of civil society, at local, state, and global levels, whose aim is to “mediate between government and the power of capital” in order to “claim and retain the rights and entitlements of state and global citizenship” (Grewal, 2009: 143).

Roy's is a voice from the global South purposefully undoing Sanctioned ignorances, crossing borders of gender, caste, and class, of the nation state, of the South/North divide. Breaking taboos against complicating the lives of the haves and the have-nots—breaking the decorum of the institutionalized academy—Roy's writing lays bare the workings of power without permission from “the experts.” A feminist, but no bourgeois one, she gives herself to the cause of the people while expressing her wariness of the “traditional, mainstream” and “strangely unbending” Left with its rigid ideology. No wonder Roy ruffles so many feathers and is often looked down by the bourgeoisie.

What makes Roy compelling in our context is that she stakes her claim in multiple citizenships and in the accountability or responsibility that attends them—Indian citizenship; global capitalist citizenship (or as a “subject of Empire”); and a democratic feminist-humanitarian people's citizenship of the world. Few have *publicly* claimed multiple citizenships so flamboyantly, claiming all of her citizens' “rights to express dissent” (Roy, 2001: 87). It is no surprise that she is the acclaimed writer of the growing global justice movement: she has staged herself as a global citizen voicing the discourse of human rights in a bold, lyrical, and impassioned way.

It is insightful to trace how the author of *The God of Small Things* (Roy, 1997) become the advocate of big things like democracy and justice? According to Gurleen Grewal, there is a continuity between these two aspects of Roy. In fact it is by continuing to do “in the public sphere what she had done with the private sphere of home and family in her novel,” (Cited in Grewal, 2009: 144) that Roy has given voice to the colonised. Uma Narayan's definition of the feminist daughter's political enterprise, to “retell the story of a mother-culture in feminist terms,” is highly appropriate for understanding Roy's work as a whole: “It is a political attempt to tell a counter-story that contests dominant narratives that would claim the entire edifice of ‘our Culture’ and ‘our Nation’ for themselves, converting them into a peculiar form of property, and excluding the voices, concerns,

and contributions of many who are members of the national and political community” (Grewal, 2009: 144).

It may be noted that Roy is the latest among an increasing number of global feminist voices that have interrogated the neoliberal policies of economic globalization. For Roy, the questions are basic and important: who benefits? Who pays the cost? “What is it [globalization] going to do to a country like India, in which social inequality has been institutionalized in the caste system for centuries? In which three hundred million people are illiterate” (Roy, 2001:13–4). Roy’s analysis of the predicament of the poor in India has been preceded by that of feminist scholars who have worked in the areas of development for over two decades: the work of Gita Sen, Peggy Antrobus, Rajni Kothari, Bina Agarwal, Vandana Shiva, and others (Grewal, 2009).

In the epigraph to *The God of Small Things*, Roy quotes John Berger: “Never again will a single story be told as though it is the only one.” In a sense, Roy’s novel is about the ecology of being, showing how everything and everyone is interconnected, and how each life is shaped by what happens to others. The novel is moving because it gives nearly all the characters, even the oppressive ones, a vulnerability and humanity: a character may be twisted, but not inherently evil.

The author of *The God of Small Things* has become a passionate critique and a powerful voice for the subaltern and for the marginalised in a post-colonial situation. This takes us to a more powerful story situated in Australia.

b. David Malouf: Remembering Babylon

Another unique approach to the use of cultural hybridity in a postcolonial text has been utilized by David Malouf, in his novel *Remembering Babylon* (Malouf 1993). Malouf writes of the formative years of an Australian settler colony, and he uses a very unique character, that of Gemmy, to illustrate the vast differences between the settlers and the aboriginals, and,

eventually, between the settlers themselves. Gemmy is a white man who has grown up amongst the aboriginals. He has been away from Western society for so long that he is unable to communicate competently, or effect legitimate social discourse with the other whites. He comes to live with a young settler colony, and Malouf uses him to illustrate differences between all members of this colony. As each member of the colony tries to analyze the differences between themselves and Gemmy, they come to realize fundamental differences amongst them all. As Mr. Frazer writes in his logbook, “We must rub our eyes and look again, clear our minds of what we are looking for to see what is there” (Malouf 130 and Hybridity 2010).

Surely, each member of a postcolonial society would love to encounter one specific voice which could articulate their particular suffering and oppression under the colonial institution-one voice which would articulate their own sense of national identity. But exploration of these societies, and the literature produced by postcolonial authors and poets illustrates that there is a veritable infinite number of differing circumstances inherent in each postcolonial society, and, consequently, in each piece of literature produced by postcolonial writers. If one is to read this literature in a way which will shed some light on the postcolonial condition, one must understand and adopt the theory that we are all walking amalgamations of our own unique cultures and traditions. We are all always struggling with our own identities, personal and national. We must understand that there is no “one true voice” representing an easily identifiable postcolonial condition, but, instead, each author is his or her own voice and must be read as such (Hybridity 2010).

The story takes place in the mid-19th century in a remote settlement of Queensland, Australia. One day as a group of children are playing at the edge of the village, a remarkable figure stumbles out of the bush. This dark, unkempt person (Gemmy) turns out to be a white man who fell from a ship 16 years earlier (when he was a 19-year-old sailor) and has lived with an aboriginal tribe ever since (Coulehan, 2012). He hardly

remembers English, and his culture and sensibility have become those of his adopted people.

At first Gemmy creates a sensation in the settlement and people want to help him, despite his obvious savage mentality (after all, he isn't even embarrassed by nakedness!). He goes to live with the McIvor family, whose daughter, Janet, and nephew, Lachlan Beattie, were among the children who found him. While Mrs. McIvor accepts Gemmy with Christian love, her husband Jock is sceptical (Coulehan, 2012).

In fact, it soon becomes clear that there are major tensions in the village regarding Gemmy. Has he really become "one of them" (a black)? Can he be trusted? He seems harmless enough--almost a pleasant imbecile--but perhaps it is all a subterfuge. Perhaps he is in contact with THEM (Coulehan, 2012).

Among the European settlers, there are two views of how to handle the blacks. One group believes they should simply be wiped out--every one of them killed--because they are savage, worthless, and couldn't possibly become (real) Christians. A second group has a more romantic view. They think the black people could be "tamed" and become their servants. They envision themselves as owners of large plantations (as in the southern United States) worked by multitudes of happy and harmless black servants (Coulehan, 2012).

Representatives of both groups try to win Gemmy's confidence and obtain information regarding the whereabouts and plans of the black tribes. He, however, remains silent about these matters, although pleasant and deferential toward everyone. An uneasy truce holds until one day two aboriginal people are observed visiting with Gemmy on McIvor's property. This creates an uproar, which eventually leads some of the God-fearing whites to commit acts of vandalism and to injure Gemmy (Coulehan, 2012).

To preserve the peace, the McIvors send Gemmy to live with Mrs. Hutchence, an eccentric woman who lives on the margin of

the settlement. However, he soon disappears into the wilderness, but not until he retrieves--and destroys--what he thinks are the seven pieces of paper on which Mr. Frazier, the minister, had written Gemmy's life story soon after he had emerged from the bush (Coulehan, 2012).

2. Reflections

This novel portrays a cultural chasm, rather than a cultural clash. Gemmy, imbued with the mysticism and earth-centeredness of the native Australians with whom he has spent 16 years, is (precisely as the settlers fear) no longer "white." Gemmy cannot identify with the European culture that was once his by heritage. No wonder he can hardly remember how to speak the English language (Coulehan, 2012).

The Europeans, secure in their conviction that the aboriginal people are sub-human savages, cannot even consider treating them as persons. Some of the settlers want to eliminate the blacks completely (genocide), while others would prefer simply to rule them. Gemmy slowly comes to the realization that to save himself he must return to his aboriginal "roots." Ironically, this escape doesn't work--an epilogue to the story implies that Gemmy comes to a bad end.

How much goodness is there in the human spirit? This novel primarily explores the casual, unthinking darkness that threatens to engulf us all. Yet, the story also reveals glimmers of light in many individual persons (Coulehan, 2012).

Remembering Babylon, as its title suggests, shares the earlier novel's preoccupation with language, and both explore what happens when a stranger, reared in totally other cultural circumstances, is introduced into a small, beleaguered community held together largely by a common fear of all that surrounds it (Taylor, 1993: 123-25).

Remembering Babylon's title remains an enigma until its final chapter. The bulk of the novel is set in a tiny settlement of

Scots immigrants in Queensland north of Bowen in the middle of last century (Taylor, 1993: 123-25). They are surrounded – and threatened – by rainforest inhabited by hostile Aboriginals. Everything about them is creepy, and at night they sleep as close to their guns as they do to their spouses.

And then, in a page of breathless, seemingly endless prose which it would be murder to condense, something balances on that crucial dividing fence at the edge of the rainforest, balances there for a moment, confronted by a white child with a stick aimed like a rifle, and tumbles out of the terrifying unknown into the white settlement.

Gemmy Fairley is a London slum child who survived the appalling conditions of the Industrial Revolution by becoming the “boy” (we are left to imagine some of his duties) of a London rat catcher. Escaping to sea, he is thrown overboard near the Queensland shore and lives for ten years with an Aboriginal tribe. He can neither read nor write, and can barely speak any English, but is induced to tell his story to the local parson and schoolmaster who, to his fascination, write it down.

Taken in and cared for by the family of the child who “discovered” Gemmy, he is given work, taught again to speak English, and partially integrated into the community. This is helped along by two strange women who have built a real house – as distinct from the crude shacks of the Scots – and who establish a kind of genteel “salon” which includes not only the young school teacher and some of his pupils, but also Gemmy (Taylor, 1993: 123-25).

It all falls apart. Fear grows – and violence with it – that Gemmy might be an infiltrator and spy for hostile Aboriginals. He disappears, taking with him a handful of the children’s school exercises which, being illiterate, he thinks is his appalling life as it was written down by the teacher on his arrival. And the novel leaps, for its final chapter, fifty years or so (Taylor, 1993: 123-25).

This is where the novel's title makes sense: *Remembering Babylon*. Gemmy Fairley was another language injected into the settlers' world: he was once Cockney, he was more particularly Aboriginal, above all else he was Threat. Having proved that he could exist there, he came out of Nowhere and, therefore, demonstrated that others could too. He divided the unanimity of the settlement, made them argue amongst themselves. He set tongue against tongue, and created Babel. And remembering? One of the children who encountered Gemmy that day was a girl who became a nun. The boy with the stick, her cousin (like Gemmy, an orphan, but a luckier one), became a member of State Parliament. His career is compromised, during the Great War, by the revelation that his cousin has been corresponding with a German.

The topic? How bees communicate, a subject that she has been researching in her convent. The authorities think she may be dealing in code (Taylor, 1993: 123-25).

The sudden leap in time near the book's conclusion is only one of its audacities. Some may find it unsettling; others utterly compelling. Another is the actual conclusion, as positive as anything in modern fiction in English. But then Malouf has never been afraid of the grand statement so few of his contemporaries would dare. He can do it gently, subtly, with the force of a revelation rather than a pronouncement.

Malouf's reputation is so secure nowadays that he might almost get away with anything. The real reason why he can get away with what he does is because he gets it right. *Remembering Babylon* is yet another demonstration of how right he gets it. Truth and language do not fit so well as Kant hoped they would. But in a language of great subtlety and beauty, Malouf suggests that there may be another way of bridging the gap between our minds and what we are trying to understand, so that the world can be "in touch now with its other life". Of discovering, in other words, the truth about itself.

3. Two Features of Post-Colonial, Multiple Identities

From our discussion above we pick up just two features of postcolonial identities: hybridity and utopian vision with a view to appreciate an elaborate, complex and even conflicting identities. For this we base ourselves mainly on Malouf.

Hybrid Identities through Difference

Resistance or response from a member of a colonised community: David Malouf's *Remembering Babylon* strictly speaking, a post-colonial text. Most would agree with Malouf it is certainly not an example of resistance or response from a member of a colonised community in the same vein as, several themes running through the novel which constitute elements of post-colonial discourse, leading to a possible empowerment of both the colonisers and the colonised.

The power of language: The construction of this new identity would both privilege and discriminate against the other smaller (elite) communities, who in turn took advantage its opportunities and resisted its constraints. So the identity is tied to language, which has unimaginable power.

Hybrid Culture

There is a pervasive sense of colonial guilt throughout *Remembering Babylon*, an awareness of the suspect morality of the colonial process. Like *Great Expectations*, *Babylon* recognises Australia as a potential utopia for the industrious European immigrant – unlike Dickens, however, Malouf asserts that the success of the project rests not on merely exploiting the resources available (while ignoring or displacing the indigenous people), but on reaching a kind of harmony and exchange with the landscape and with the colonised. This hybrid culture represents, for Malouf, the ideal ultimate outcome of the colonial process (Dunlop, 1997).

4. Concluding Remarks

“Our first business will be to supervise the making of fables and legends, rejecting all which are unsatisfactory; and we shall induce nurses and mothers to tell their children only those which we have approved.” – Socrates in Plato’s *Republic*

For generations, humans gathered around hearth and fire to tell and retell stories. Much of cultural transmission was in the form of storytelling. Today, people are more likely to gather around the cool glow of the television, but we are no less storied creatures. Some imaginary calculations of the amount of time and money spent on the entertainment, news, and publishing industries should give us pause to think about how central storytelling is to our humanity. To this add the everyday interactions with friends and families in which people recount events and share gossip. By my rough estimation, perhaps fifty percent or more of our waking hours is involved in storytelling. In the words of sociologist Christian Smith, humans are “animals who make stories but also animals who are *made* by our stories” (Smith, 2003: 64).

Stories always have normative content, describing what is important, what is unimportant, what is better, what is worse, what is good, and what is bad. Charles Taylor argues that stories about self and society are how humans construct the “horizons of meaning” that form the critical background for social relations and life choices. Narratives always represent a kind of movement in moral space. Narratives are the way that humans have of constructing coherence and continuity in our lives. (Taylor 1989). So they help us fashion our selfhoods through differences.

It is important to emphasize that humans can hold multiple narratives, sometimes mutually exclusive. We mix and match. The conservative Roman Catholic narrative is incompatible with the narrative of Liberal Democracy, but that does not prevent most conservative Roman Catholics from being enthusiastic supporters of Liberal Democracies. The Christian narrative appears incompatible with capitalist virtues, but that does not prevent Christians from living the bourgeois life. The eco-

romantic narrative appears incompatible with much of modern technology, but that does not prevent environmentalists from using soon to be obsolete laptops and flying around the world to enjoy ecotourism. Each generation reinterprets these narratives in different situations, even as each generation is also constituted by these received stories. People are not passive recipients of these narratives, but active reinterpreters.

The idealized past narrative above contrasts sharply with progressive, future oriented narratives, for instance the Scientific Enlightenment narrative or the Capitalist Prosperity narrative. This nostalgia narrative is woven into many of the fundamentalist religious movements today whether in the East or West, the North or South. One can argue with this nostalgia narrative, but evidence alone cannot compel someone to believe otherwise. Like all of the narratives listed and described by Christian Smith, it involves a certain reading of history and a certain set of assumptions about what really matters in life (Smith, 2003).

As contemporary philosopher William Grassie shows the greatest untruths will always be the unconscious lies that we tell ourselves, the mistaking of our own limited perspectives with the Absolute. Reinhold Niebuhr summed it up, when he quipped “The doctrine of original sin is the only empirically verifiable doctrine of Christianity” (Niebuhr 1941). To avoid sin, we should be humble, rigorous, courageous, and creative in pursuing truth (and beauty and goodness), wherever it leads. And the goal of intellectual nonviolence and postcolonial assertion of identities is to set out in as many different directions as possible, to be multiply converted to diverse metanarratives, inhabiting their truths, forgiving their failures, taking the best, and leaving the rest. This enables us to fashion multiple (even conflicting) selfhoods, respect differences and so understand ourselves – colonisers, colonised and their hybrid children – deeper.

The paradoxical observation of William Butler Yeats (1865-1939) is apt here (Yeats: 1919):

Things fall apart; the centre cannot hold;
Mere anarchy is loosed upon the world,
The blood-dimmed tide is loosed, and everywhere
The ceremony of innocence is drowned;
The best lack all conviction, while the worst
Are full of passionate intensity.
Surely some revelation is at hand...

Drawing from the multiple postcolonial identities, can we still reduce the individual and collective violence – both real and imagined – we inflict on ourselves and others due to our imaginary identities, constructed selfhood, derived self-fashioning and amplified differences? So the challenge now is to realise our own multiple and conflicting identities of the self and those of the other. Then we can enter into a creative and complex dialogue between them, enabling us to befriend the “others” in the Other and “Otherness”.

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Notes

1. This article is adapted from my paper published in Ferrao, V., & In Ponniah, J. (2013). Identity, difference and conflict: Postcolonial critique : papers presented at the ACPI Annual Research Seminar held at Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune, 26-29 October 2012.
2. Grewal, 2009: 146. Arundhati Roy is not only an accomplished novelist, but equally gifted in unraveling the politics of globalization, the power and ideology of corporate culture, fundamentalism, terrorism, and other issues gripping today's world. This volume – featuring prominent scholars from throughout the world – examines Roy beyond the aesthetic parameters of her fiction, focusing also on her creative activism and struggles in global politics. The chapters travel to and fro between her non-fictional works – engaging activism on the streets and global forums – and its underlying roots in her novel. Roy is examined as a novelist, non-fiction writer, journalist, activist, feminist, screenwriter, ideologist, and architect. This volume presents Roy's interlocking network of the ideas, attitudes and ideologies that emerge from the contemporary social and the political world.

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Article Received: November 28, 2018

Article Accepted: January 12, 2021

No of Words: 4200

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